

NEON -Next Generation Integrated Energy Services for Citizen Energy Communities

WP 1- Integrated energy service co-creation and cross-sectoral arrangements

D1.3 Specification of multi-actor interaction across sector

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Executive summary

This document covers the NEON Project's analysis and preliminary development of possible cross sectoral arrangements in the NEON Project pre-selected citizen energy communities (CECs), as part of Task 1.3 - *Specification of multi-actor interaction across sectors*. Firstly, it gives an overview of the different multi actors present in the transitioning energy market and a general assessment of the cross sectoral arrangements between these actors inside of an energy community. Then, it tackles the objective of this deliverable to report potential interaction scenarios and strategies to engage stakeholders in the cross-sectoral arrangements that will allow the studied CECs to exploit energy efficiency and demand flexibility. In doing so, this deliverable will identify suitable means to influence user behaviour and will explain how corresponding business models will be supported in practice.

Finally, during this process, each CECs were requested to develop with the support of the technical partners different strategies to implement in practice the energy services identified in the previous deliverables D1.1 and D1.2 and that are being evaluated to be deployed in their CEC. Thus, from the identification of the energy services in T1.1 and the interviews to the stakeholders performed in T1.2 to identify their needs and wants, in T1.3 preliminary strategies and typology of arrangements were identified to put them in practice in the 4 pilot CECs mapping also user's requirements, technical requirements and grid relevant aspects to be considered for their implementation.

This document sets in its conclusion part of the basis for the work that will be carried out in WP2 where more details will be developed in the financial and contractual aspects of the cross-sectoral arrangements and in WP3 in terms of technical implementations to serve in practice these energy services in the CECs.

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Abbreviations and acronyms

AEC	Azienda Elettrica Comunale – Municipal Electricity Company
ARERA	Autorità di Regolazione per Energia Reti e Ambiente - Regulatory Authority for Energy Networks and Environment
CEC	Citizen Energy Community
CEP	Clean Energy Package
CfD	Contracts for Differences
DR	Demand Response
DSO	Distribution System Operator
EPC	Energy Performance Contract
ESCo	Energy Service Company
ESO	Energy Service Operator
EU	European Union
EV	Electric Vehicle
GO	General Objective
HVAC	Heating, Ventilation and Air Conditioning
MiSE	Ministero dello Sviluppo Economico - Ministry of Economic Development
P2P	Peer-to-Peer
P4P	Pay For Performance
POD	Point Of Delivery
PPA	Power Purchase Agreement
PV	Photovoltaic
SaaS	Software as a Service
SMEs	Small and Medium Enterprises
SO	Specific Objective

T	Task
ToU	Time-of-Use
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

1.1 Background

Traditionally, electric energy is generated by large, centralized plants located far from the consumption centres and then transported via high and medium voltage lines that travel hundreds of kilometres to reach end users. This type of scheme is known as Centralized Generation. Due to economic, safety or environmental factors, the electric energy production facilities are located close to the source of the energy resources.

Ever since the world's first power grid was inaugurated, attempts have been made to find a different form of generation where humans can generate and consume their own energy at nearby points. For many decades, this solution was not cost-effective.

However, today, distributed generation is a reality that is becoming increasingly popular, with significant advantages. Utilizing this approach, users generate, consume, and sell energy to the grid. By generating energy very close to the point of consumption, energy losses in distribution are reduced. For example, electricity or hot water can be generated on residential rooftops, or heat for hot water or heating from geothermal systems installed in the foundations of buildings. Distributed generation is directly related to small-scale photovoltaic or thermal generation in cities and therefore to self-consumption in buildings. In addition to photovoltaic, thermal, and small-scale wind power generation, distributed generation includes distributed cogeneration, which make use of electricity and thermal energy in the form of steam or hot water, and trigeneration, which also generates cooling. This type of generation is mainly carried out in industrial centres or in housing districts with local distribution networks for electricity, heat or cold.

Distributed generation offers several advantages over centralized generation. From a technical point of view, distributed generation is connected directly to the distribution network, avoiding the need to go through the transmission network to deliver the electricity to the final consumer. This reduces electricity losses. From the point of view of system management, self-consumption of electricity allows the end consumer to make maximum use of the energy resource, thus reducing the difficulties between the management of electricity supply and demand.

Furthermore, on 30 November 2016, the European Commission published the Clean Energy Package for all Europeans [1], a set of legislative acts redesigning the energy sector through measures for energy efficiency, renewables, electricity market design, security of electricity

supply and governance rules for the Energy Union to reach the Renewable energy targets for 2030:

- cut greenhouse gas emissions by at least 40% (compared to 1990).
- reach 32% share of renewable energy.
- reduce consumptions by 32.5% as a target for energy efficiency.

In the Clean Energy Package, the concept of the Energy Community was introduced, providing for two different models: the Citizen Energy Community (CEC) and the Renewable Energy Community (REC) [1]. Both envisage the possibility for community members to collectively engage in the production, distribution, supply, consumption, sharing, storage, and sale of self-produced energy. More generally, the intention is to promote the development and acceptance of RES at the local level, energy efficiency, end-user market participation and to facilitate the provision of affordable energy to counteract energy vulnerability and poverty with positive environmental, economic, and social impacts. In contrast to CEC, the REC solution involves the supply of renewable energy only, and the conversion of the latter into different energy carriers, i.e., electricity, heat, and cooling energy. Other differences between the two types of energy community concern the organisational model, participation and control, and the area of application.

1.2 Document's objectives and relation to other tasks

The deliverable 1.3 *"Specification of multi-actor interaction across sectors"* is a result of the work carried out within task 1.3 - *Cross-sectoral arrangements and stakeholder interaction* - from month 4 to month 12 within the WP1 - *Integrated energy service co-creation and cross-sectoral arrangements*.

NEON Project's objective is to advance the leveraging technologies, concepts, and business ecosystem for integrated next-generation integrated energy services for European Communities to enhance life quality of European citizens while improving the performance of the energy system. In particular, the objective of this specific document is to report on the established cross-sectoral arrangements in terms of multi-actor interaction between grid stakeholders, service providers and consumers. Therefore, T1.3 is mainly linked to NEON's **GO2: Develop efficient business models and contracting schemes across different market segments and actors in the value chain** by identifying the suitable cross-sectoral arrangements to be implemented in the CECs.

More specifically, T1.3 will tackle NEON's **SO** presented in Table 1 below.

Table 1 NEON’s Specific Objectives (SO)

Acronym	Description
SO2:	<p>Develop effective business models and contracting schemes across different stakeholders.</p> <p>NEON will enable innovative business models by joining EPC and P4P contracting schemes across sectors, and demonstrate their effectiveness, applicability and adaptability to different business, regulatory and contractual frameworks.</p> <p>NEON will create new business opportunities at the grid level through economic savings coupled with energy and non-energy benefits, achieved by unlocking demand flexibility to bring benefits from both the grid and consumer side, enabling them to interact with the grid and the energy market. The effectiveness of the business models will be demonstrated within the Citizen Energy Communities (CECs) engaged in NEON, while lessons learnt will be exploited in the development of replication plans.</p>
SO5:	<p>Maximize the exploitation of energy efficiency through improved building operation. By exploiting integration with building systems, NEON will provide an optimal control strategy to maximise the exploitation of energy efficiency on the demand side and the positive impact of multi-measure energy efficiency interventions on the demand side by improving building operational performance through advanced control capabilities and optimal building systems operation. By improving building operations, NEON will facilitate service providers in delivering contracted energy and cost savings to consumers, as well as unlocking the potential for flexibility as part of ancillary grid services.</p>

As illustrated in Figure 1, T1.3 is closely linked to the other tasks of WP1 which results reported in the deliverables will serve as baseline for the following work packages WP2 and WP3.

D1.3 is built on top of the service cross integration process made in **Task 1.2** that set the basis of the CEC’s preliminary business planning by interviewing local stakeholders, identifying revenue opportunities, and setting up financial mechanisms. In particular, D1.3 analyses the agreements made between involved stakeholders to exploit energy efficiency and demand flexibility based on the preliminary identified mechanisms for benefits bundling provided in **D1.1**.

This will imply the interaction between grid stakeholders/utilities and service providers in terms of leveraging the energy efficiency and unlocking the demand flexibility as part of the grid ancillary services (e.g., under bilateral P4P arrangements). With a special focus to the interaction between grid stakeholder and service providers on one side, and the consumers on another, in terms of energy and service provision (e.g., while combining EPC and P4P).

In particular, the aim of this activity was to identify suitable means to influence user behaviour and how corresponding business models will be supported in practice. Their possible applications were then evaluated in the context of the project’s 4 pilot sites considering user requirements, relevant aspects of the network and links to building efficiency retrofits.

This deliverable also worked closely with:

- D1.4 in which the strategy for engagement with CECs is presented and that provides the consumer requirements as a result of field survey.
- D1.5 that reports the design principles of NEON platform and the key performance indicators to assess the services in operation.
- D2.2 that sets the Guidelines and reports on innovative energy performance contracting models combined with pay-for-performance schemas across different stakeholders.

Figure 1 Relation between project's tasks

1.3 Document's structure

In summary, the main objectives of Task 1.3 were to:

1. Define stakeholders' interaction scenarios.
2. Develop strategies to exploit energy efficiency and demand flexibility.
3. Specify multi-actor interactions.
4. Engage stakeholders in cross-sectoral arrangements.

Therefore, in order to tackle these 4 objectives, firstly the multi-sector actors present in the electricity market were assessed developing their roles and responsibilities, and a general overview of the possible cross-sectoral arrangements between these different actors was performed. Then, based on the preliminary state of art made, some strategies to exploit the energy efficiency and demand flexibility were developed from a social engagement, technical, economic, and financial point of view in order to finally adapt them to the CECs involved in the NEON project.

D1.3 reports the work carried out in T1.3 as follows:

- **Chapter 1** introduces the deliverable D1.3 by giving a short background on the electricity market context, an overview of NEON's objectives related to task T1.3 and the structure of this document.
- **Chapter 2** gives a general overview of the multi sector actors that play a role in the energy service market in order to introduce the specific stakeholders that could engage in cross-sectoral arrangements in each CEC involved in the project.
- **Chapter 3** assesses the main general cross-sectoral arrangements between grid stakeholders/utilities and service providers, and between service providers and the community.
- **Chapter 4** analyses the strategies for possible cross-sectoral arrangements to exploit the energy efficiency and demand flexibility and how they will be supported in practice from a social engagement, technical, economic, and financial point of view.
- **Chapter 5** tailors the strategies for possible cross-sectoral arrangements for each energy service identified in each CEC in task T1.1 and each stakeholder interviewed in T1.2 in order to analyse their possible strategies and processes for their deployment.
- **Section 6** summarises the work carried out in T1.3 and sets the conclusion of this deliverable.

2 Multi sector actors (Roles, responsibilities, etc.)

In the progress of energy transition, the variety of playing actors in the electricity sector increased and it is of central importance to identify and assess their roles and contributions to the deployment and development of CECs in Europe.

In economic terms, a market player is considered to be any natural or legal person who intervenes in economic transactions taking place in a market. The players in the energy saving and efficiency sector can be summarised as follows:

- **Public Administrations** which activity consists in the development of energy saving and efficiency regulations (strategies, savings targets, subsidies, technical regulation) and in the consumption of efficient services and products itself.
- **Manufacturers** of components and final products who are persons (usually a legal entity) that engage in a manufacturing activity for the production of goods to be consumed by final end-consumers.
- **Savings and efficiency service companies** are organizations that provide services related to energy consumption at a user's premises. This group includes the following companies Energy Services, Energy Certification, Energy Auditors, Consultants, Verification Companies, etc.
- **Financial Institutions** which activity consists of financing savings and efficiency projects.
- **Energy suppliers** who are in charge of supplying energy to the final consumer. It should be noted that the Energy Service Companies (ESCOs) can act as energy suppliers as part of their energy service contract.

This chapter focuses and gives a general overview of the following multi sector actors that play a role in the electricity market:

- in Section 2.1 Grid stakeholders/utilities (DSOs, DNOs, TSOs, ...).
- in Section 2.2 Service Providers (ESCOs, DR Aggregators, ...).
- in Section 2.3 Communities (End users (consumers and prosumers), SMEs, Industries, Public Administrations, ...).
- in Section 2.4 Energy Service Operators (ESOs).

This chapter serves as well as introduction of chapter 5 where the specific stakeholders that could engage in cross-sectoral arrangements in each CEC involved in the project will be analysed.

2.1 Grid stakeholders/utilities (DSOs, DNOs, TSOs, ...)

Initially, a review of the stakeholders in the modern energy system was performed. An overview of the industry stakeholders with specific considerations of their interests in Energy communities is given below. This review and these key stakeholder groups informed the establishment of the Stakeholder Ecosystem. Stakeholders can be separated into several groups operating at different points in the energy market and thus representing different perspectives.

Existing stakeholder groups were evaluated, and their memberships reviewed to help identify stakeholder contacts. Example groups include:

- **European Distribution System Operators (E.DSO).** E.DSO is a network of 42 DSOs over 23 countries with a focus on reliability in the electricity supply of Europe. The current membership is listed on their website [2].
- **European Network of Transmission System Operators for Electricity (ENTSO-E).** ENTSO-E represents 43 TSOs from 36 countries in Europe. ENTSO-E was established and given legal mandates by the EU's Third Legislative Package for the Internal Energy Market in 2009, which aims at further liberalizing the gas and electricity markets in the EU. The current membership is listed on their website [3].

An overview of separated grid stakeholder groups is presented below:

- **System Operator.** The main responsibility of this entity is to balance the supply and demand of electricity in real time. Based on specific country regulations and market arrangement, this can be the Transmission System Operator (TSO) or Distribution System Operator (DSO), with attributions over the planning, building and operation of the transmission system / distribution system,
- **DSO.** The DSO maintains connections for customers and carries out the distribution of electricity (at voltage levels of 150 kV or less). Furthermore, the DSO installs, maintains, and operates the classified distribution grids to ensure that energy suppliers can always meet the ever-changing energy needs. DSOs are impartial, so they can guarantee non-discriminatory access to third parties. Integration of decentralised generation (mostly connected to distribution networks) and of prosumers obliges modernising of the role of the DSOs. The traditional role of operating and maintaining the distribution system is not adequate anymore as further active grid development, management and operation are required yet at the same time offer more opportunities for the DSOs to manage their grids in more flexible and efficient ways. DSOs see an active role for their companies, based on the fact that an important part of the benefits of DR lie at the DSO level.

- **TSO.** The TSO is responsible for guaranteeing the safe technical operation of the power system. The key task is to preserve the balance between electricity supply and demand at any time. Moreover, the TSO is responsible for transferring electricity on a national or regional level, using infrastructure like high voltage (HV) power lines and stations. Because of the nature of the grid and the high costs of establishing transmission infrastructure, a TSO is a natural monopoly and is frequently solely or partly owned by national governments. TSOs are independent from electricity generation companies and electricity distribution companies and are financed mostly through charging a fee proportional to the energy they transport. In addition to transmission, the TSO also maintains the security of the grid in real time to prevent fluctuations in frequency. The TSO preserves an uninterrupted balance between electricity supply from power stations and demand from end-users; and ensures enough emergency and reserve power is committed to allow for unexpected contingencies. Different TSOs have different roles in DR. Commonly, the role of the TSO is to open up necessary control mechanisms in such a way that the market has access and acts in line with the needs of the TSO (e.g., parties pay for imbalance created and rewarded for solving imbalance problems, thus the capacity of secondary or tertiary reserve power is considerably reduced).
- **Distribution Network Operator.** These are companies licensed to distribute electricity from the transmission grid to homes and businesses. In some countries their role is merged with the SO. The DNO will have increasing roles in balancing parts of the network and in managing network constraints through flexibility services
- **Supplier/Retailer.** Supplier is a company selling electricity to consumers (end users). Specific functions of a supplier service will include purchasing electricity on wholesale market, billing, customer management, meter data reconciliation. The energy retailer holds the contract with the end-user, organizationally delivers the energy and is responsible for purchasing the provided electricity bilaterally. More specifically, the role of the retailer is to buy electricity on the wholesale market and to resell it to small-scale consumers.
- **Micro grid operator.** A principal purpose of the micro grid operator is to transition the system into decentralised-mode operation when appropriate and to ensure system stability by balancing load and generation during the islanded mode operation. The micro grid operator can operate in both grid-connected and autonomously.
- **Balance Responsible Party (BRP).** Administratively, the supplier buys the energy from the producers through bilateral agreements or through an energy market and sells the energy to the end-user. Since imbalance between supply and demand would lead to physical problems with the grid and electricity supplying, BRPs are in charge of ensuring that the amount of power consumed matches the energy produced within their portfolio. The physical balancing though is done by the TSO and the TSO penalizes BRP's for creating any

imbalances. BRPs will want to know how future electricity networks will affect their role and the accuracy with which they can predict imbalances.

- **Generation.** As defined by 2009/72/EC, a producer is a natural or legal person generating electricity and contributing actively to voltage and reactive power control. The producer produces energy that is fed into the energy grid while aiming to operate its assets at maximum efficiency. Through the introduction of renewable energy, the position of centralized power plants changed in the merit order of production. RES have almost zero short-term marginal costs that gives an advantage over fuel-based power plants on the energy market. Generation parties will be interested in the potential penetration levels of various technologies operating on the grid and the bandwidth available for variable and stable generation operating at different timescales.

2.2 Service Providers (ESCOs, DR Aggregators, ...)

Energy service providers (ESCOs), as currently defined in Europe, are organizations that provide energy services at a given user's facilities, with payment for services being based on the achievement of energy savings. These savings will be achieved through the implementation of measures to improve energy efficiency and energy consumption savings in the facilities or using renewable energy sources.

The scope of action of these companies is very broad, since they can cover all possible energy services, with the sole purpose of improving the efficiency of energy use and reducing the energy costs of a facility. ESCOs can thus design, finance, install, commission, and control a given project, assuming all or part of the technical and economic risk of the project.

The development of this type of business began in the United States in the 1970s, as a possible solution to the increase in energy costs that the country suffered at that time. Initially, the service was not very well received by large energy consumers, mainly due to their mistrust of the real reduction in energy consumption proposed. Precisely this distrust was the basis for the design of the Energy Service Companies (ESCO) model, ensuring and guaranteeing the obtaining of energy savings, and financing the service based on these savings. In the following years, the service took on great prominence in the U.S. in the 1990s, with the development of new energy-efficient technologies for energy efficiency in lighting systems, air conditioning, bioclimatic architecture, etc. Thus, ESCOs found an important place in the energy market, having developed a multitude of relevant projects in this country, both in public and private facilities.

Currently, ESCOs and their business model have a wide international development and are beginning to develop and find their position also in Europe. Some countries, such as Germany,

Canada, and the USA, have extensive experience in these services and are also beginning to export their business models to other countries.

At the end of 2008, the European Parliament approved the triple objective "20-20-20", which consists of reducing primary energy consumption in the European Union by 20% by 2020 compared to 1990 levels, reducing greenhouse gas emissions by a further 20% and increasing the contribution of renewable energies to 20% of consumption. In short, the 20-20-20 objective includes a commitment to reduce greenhouse gases and focuses on two priority ways of achieving it: energy saving and efficiency and renewable energies. The promotion of the development of Energy Service Companies is one of the cross-cutting measures that will be implemented through the energy saving and efficiency plans, promoting them by guaranteeing their legal security, facilitating their financing, and encouraging the public contracting of these services. However, it is likely that in the future an additional economic incentive will be necessary so that the return periods of the investments to be made by the ESCOs will be shorter and, therefore, the entry into this service market will be more attractive.

The implementation of services provided by an ESCO contributes directly to the community objectives of energy saving and promotion of renewable energies. Through its services, energy savings can be obtained in large installations that can reach levels of savings between 25 and 40% of consumption, improving the installations and without reducing their environmental quality. Thus, improving the energy efficiency of these facilities can make a clear contribution to saving energy consumption.

The services of ESCOs also have a great potential in the market given their high ease of financing for the client and their model similar to "turnkey" projects. The services of an ESCO have the capacity to combine all the necessary services to obtain energy savings, thus representing an improvement and sale of energy savings. This integration of services allows the client to outsource the design, implementation, operation, and maintenance of a project. This integration of services allows the client to outsource all the energy requirements of his company, focusing on the central activity of his installation, thus being more energy and operationally efficient.

Description of the energy services that can be offered by an ESCO

The services provided by an ESCO are of a wide variety. In fact, all services that allow energy and/or economic savings to be achieved for a facility or building could be included in the scope of an ESCO's services. Thus, both the simplest services, such as controlling the temperature of a building, and other more complex and technological measures that require greater investment, such as the installation of its own renewable energy source, would be within its scope.

All services can be independent of each other or can be developed jointly and complementarily by the same ESCO. Joint development is precisely one of the advantages of the service provided by an ESCO.

The scope of services provided by an ESCO allows the client to have a single interlocutor and to outsource all the required services to a single organization.

The scope of an ESCO's services is therefore adapted to the client's needs in each case. In companies with extensive experience in energy matters, an ESCO may simply develop the construction and installation of a specific project, or only develop the operation of a previously installed project. However, in cases where companies wish to completely outsource the energy aspects of their business in order to focus on their core business, an ESCO can develop all the services offered together.

Next, with the aim of identifying all the services that an ESCO could develop, a description of what would be an integral energy service will be made, understood as one that includes all the types of energy services offered by an ESCO. For a better understanding, a chronological description of the phases of execution of the service is made from the first approach and contracting of the service of this type of projects until the end of the service.

Main target facilities for the implementation of energy services

The services provided by an ESCO are usually services that require a significant economic investment. This investment must also be financed from the energy savings achieved, so the facilities in which these services can be implemented must be large facilities, with significant energy consumption (intensive in energy consumption) that allow for the amortization of the investment.

In this way, and according to the trend in international countries with greater experience in these services, the facilities in which these services have been most implemented are buildings such as hospitals, shopping centres, universities and schools, sports facilities or large business centres or office buildings. The industrial sector should also be considered, as well as other public administration facilities and residences.

These services could also be developed in smaller facilities, as long as the efforts and investments in several facilities can be combined at the same time, so that the investment can be amortized with the energy savings achieved. As an example, for the implementation of these services in single-family houses, it could be feasible to organize a pool of houses in which an energy service would be implemented jointly. Thus, the investment in installations and equipment could be centralized and more easily amortized from the savings achieved.

Even though they may perform similar activities, it is important not to confuse the concept of energy service company with that of Energy Service Provider Company (ESPC), as there are some specificities present in Energy Service Companies:

- ESCOs guarantee energy savings and/or the provision of the same energy service at a lower cost by executing energy efficiency projects.
- The benefits of ESCOs are directly associated with the energy savings achieved.
- ESCOs can finance or help obtain financing for the installation by offering future energy savings as a guarantee.
- ESCOs participate in the subsequent operation of the facility by measuring and verifying the savings achieved over the period of time that the facility is in operation.

On some occasions, the Energy Services Company may require the realization of a previous energy diagnosis of the building or installation, in order to have a first approximation of the potential savings.

One of the fundamental phases is control, measurement, and verification since the success of the project and of the ESCO's business model depends on the success of the project and the savings achieved. Therefore, it is necessary to carry out a consumption to verify that the expected savings are being achieved.

In the event that they are not verified at the desired level, this monitoring allows corrective measures to be taken.

The source of financing is one of the elements that define the contract between the ESCO and the end user. Financing by the ESCO presents undoubted advantages for the customer, since:

- The customer maintains its debt and investment capacity available for the development of its own activity without affecting its financial statements with the implementation of energy efficiency projects.
- At the end of the contract, the customer will be the owner of an energy-efficient installation without the need for an investment effort.

Energy service companies face a certain degree of economic risk since the payment for the services provided is based (partly or fully) on the achievement of energy efficiency improvements and the fulfilment of other agreed performance requirements. The customer, however, has the possibility of economic benefit from optimizing its energy consumption while reducing the risk of energy price fluctuations, all without the need for any investment. The services provided by an ESCO are of a wide variety. In fact, all the services that make it possible to achieve energy and/or economic savings for an installation, without the need for any investment, could be included in the scope of action of an ESCO.

Among the types of agents involved in this business are installation companies, maintenance companies, engineering companies, energy consulting firms and energy suppliers. In addition, there are public and private energy service companies.

2.3 Communities (End users (consumers and prosumers), SMEs, Industries, Public Administrations, ...)

This section provides an overview of the roles and responsibilities of Citizen Energy Communities (CECs) within the electricity sector, as established by the Directive (EU) 2019/944 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 June 2019 on common rules for the internal market for electricity and amending Directive 2012/27/EU.

As established in the mentioned Directive, a 'citizen energy community' means a legal entity that: may engage in generation, including from renewable sources, distribution, supply, consumption, aggregation, energy storage, energy efficiency services or charging services for electric vehicles or provide other energy services to its members or shareholders.

Therefore, the scope of action of CECs is broad.

Article 16 of the mentioned Directive, develops further the concept of CECs, from which we can highlight:

- The role of CECs to engage actors not traditionally involved in the energy sector, as the participation in these entities is open and voluntary (art. 16.1.a)
- The possibility that CECs, if Member States consider so in their transposition, own, establish, purchase or lease distribution networks and autonomously manage them subject to conditions established in the Directive (art. 16.2.b)
- That member states shall ensure that CECs are able to access all electricity markets, either directly or through aggregation, in a non-discriminatory manner (art. 16.3.a)
- That member states shall ensure that CECs are treated in a non-discriminatory and proportionate manner with regard to their activities, rights and obligations as final customers, producers, suppliers, distribution system operators or market participants engaged in aggregation (art. 16.3.b)
- That member states shall ensure that CECs are financially responsible for the imbalances they cause in the electricity system; to that extent they shall be balance responsible parties or shall delegate their balancing responsibility in accordance with Article 5 of Regulation (EU) 2019/943 (art. 16.3.c)
- That member states shall ensure that with regard to consumption of self-generated electricity, citizen energy communities are treated like active customers in accordance with point (e) of Article 15(2) (art. 16.3.d)
- That member states shall ensure that CECs are entitled to arrange within the citizen energy community the sharing of electricity that is produced by the production units owned by the community, subject to other requirements laid down in this Article and

subject to the community members retaining their rights and obligations as final customers (art. 16.3.d)

The specific manners in which those aspects covered within article 16 will be delivered, will depend on how each member state transposes the aforementioned Directive.

In the early stages of development, we can observe that CECs are mainly engaging in collective self-consumption activities. In this respect, the scope of action of these actors will largely depend on the national regulation. It remains to be seen how the previously highlighted article 16.3.d is transposed into national framework, in particular with regards to the ownership of the production units, that the Directive indicates that should be owned by the CECs, in order to arrange the sharing of the produced electricity.

In certain markets, such as in Spain, we can also observe in these early stages that CECs not only develop collective self-consumption schemes, but also sustainable mobility initiatives, both in the form of developing charging infrastructure and purchasing shared electric vehicles.

Within the CECs of larger scale, commercialisation of electricity might as well be a key activity, although the barriers of entry to develop this activity are high, given the expertise and financial back-up necessary to enter this segment.

With regards to aggregation, CECs would be in a good position to provide these services, although at the moment the national regulatory frameworks are under development.

On the role of CECs as DSOs, it is the discretion of each member state whether they can develop or not this activity.

Finally, CECs can provide services involving energy storage and energy efficiency, although in practical terms these activities are not very present within the scope of CECs. It is part of the objective of this project to make a proposition for CECs that enables energy efficiency to be a core aspect of their projects. We can see, in countries such as Ireland, that energy efficiency is set as the priority activity of these actors.

A key element of the role of CECs is to provide social benefits to local actors and community, as inferred by its definition in the Directive that states that “a CEC has for its primary purpose to provide environmental, economic or social community benefits to its members or shareholders or to the local areas where it operates rather than to generate financial profits”. Hence, it is important not only to contemplate their role within the electricity sector, but more broadly. This means that CECs can play an important social role in relation to how they achieve a higher

acceptance of renewable energy technologies or on how their members decide to spend their benefits (e.g., subsidising the costs of electricity of vulnerable CEC members or in a situation of energy poverty).

2.4 ESOs (Energy Services Operators)

The Electricity System Operator (ESO) plays a central role in the energy system. It performs several relevant functions:

- the real-time operation of the system.
- market development.
- connection's management.
- advising on network investment.

A core function of the ESO is balancing the grid in a safe, reliable, and efficient way, providing the second-by-second balancing of electricity supply and demand. Balancing the grid is a highly complex activity. The role of the ESO is to ensure electricity supply meets demand second by second. Electricity is transported to all corners of a Country. For this reason, the most critical parameters, like voltage and frequency, must be carefully regulated across the whole network to ensure that the power generated at scale in industrial power stations can be safely used by domestic appliances too. This must be done smoothly and efficiently, by providing ancillary services that keep the electricity supply reliable, affordable, and safe.

The electricity demand is unpredictable and can change quickly: it rises and falls throughout the day, it is affected by weather and seasons and then about supply too. The ESO uses the balancing mechanism to balance supply and demand on a national network. This mechanism is used to buy and procure the right amount of electricity required to balance supply and demand in real time. The balancing mechanism is a continuously open online auction, with thousands of trades issued daily. For every trading period, the balancing mechanism signals how much it will cost to provide power at that time. During the auction, market participants submit offers. At gate closure, the market closes for the trading period. Offers are accepted. The balancing mechanism data are assessed, constantly reviewing offers, and issuing instructions to keep the system in balance and the frequency stable.

Therefore, the ESO provides the most value to consumers, protecting them from undue costs, enabling safe cost-effective decarbonisation, being the trusted source of information and insights.

The Energy System Operator has a significant role to play in the transition to a decarbonised, decentralised, and digitalised energy system. Concerning data and digitalisation, it is responsible for providing information to market participants to facilitate informed decision-making and for ensuring the efficient operation of the system. The ESO is expected to do this transparently and in a user-friendly manner.

The changing nature of generation, particularly the increase in small generation connected at the distribution level is highlighting the need for a more holistic and coordinated approach to planning and operating the transmission and distribution systems. The increase in new sources of flexibility also means there is a need for the Energy System Operator to review how it procures these services.

The ESO's role needs to develop, to ensure it is well placed to both respond to and help facilitate the transformation of the electricity system over the coming decades.

3 Cross-sectoral Arrangements

This chapter introduces the concept of **Pay-for-Performance (P4P)** which concerns arrangements between different stakeholders in a CEC. A Pay-for-Performance scheme is a way to achieve significant, larger-scale energy savings in the European building stock and attract additional investments and new business models (see NEON D2.2 - "Multi-actor energy performance contracting").

This approach encourages long-term investment and transparent cash-flows (pay) in energy efficient buildings by metering energy savings smart and getting return-of-investment based on proven and measured savings in the buildings (performance).

The P4P-concept in NEON is strongly related to the active role of prosumers and aggregators in the context of innovative integrated energy services, maximizing the benefits related to grid stability. These performance-based incentives, even integrated into EPCs, will be aimed at incentivising the persistence of energy savings over time, boosting the market for energy services, also by supporting utilities, ESCOs, and aggregators in the innovation of their business to promote integrated energy services to their clients.

The consumers will experience reduced energy bills owing to the energy efficiency interventions and optimal asset control, and receive incentives for manual interventions (e.g., for manual influencing the demand curve). The service providers will benefit from services fees (e.g., depending on the contracted share of energy savings) and payments for unlocked flexibility and automated DR mechanisms under P4P arrangements made with utilities, while the grid stakeholders will profit from reduced maintenance and operation costs owing to the improved grid stability and lower transmission losses because of the higher local RES hosting capacity.

P4P will work on two levels:

- the relation between utilities and service providers/ESCOs/aggregators, supporting the reduction of energy demand by aggregation of prosumers.
- the relation between service providers/ESCOs/aggregators and CECs, providing energy efficiency interventions, optimised control actions and load shifting activities, and the resulting economics savings.

A P4P based on a bidding program may be set up to allow implementers to compete for contracts on the reduction of energy demand, to efficiently align forecasted energy savings to the targets of the projects. On the other side, Standard-offer P4P mechanisms may be integrated into EPCs between implementers and CECs. These blended mid-to-long term contracts will offer a clear technical and economic framework to CECs members to deliver multi-measure energy efficiency interventions and related energy savings (via EPCs) and performance-based incentives (via P4P), thanks to explicit (quantity-based) and implicit (price-based) DR mechanisms.

3.1 Between grid stakeholders/utilities and service providers

A Power Purchase Agreement (PPA) is a long-term electricity supply agreement between two parties, usually between an electricity producer (seller) and a consumer or electricity distributor (buyer). PPA defines in detail all the terms and conditions for the sale and purchase of electricity, including the volume of electricity from the supply, negotiated prices, the balance between production and consumption and penalties in the case of breach of contract.

The stipulation of a PPA requires the definition, allocation, and management of the most typical risks of long-term projects:

- **market risk**, i.e., the possibility that market prices, in a given area or because of balancing charges, fall short of the value defined in the contract.
- **counterparty risk**, i.e., the possibility that a counterparty is unable to collect, pay or supply the amount of energy agreed-upon.
- **volume risk**, i.e., in the event of difficulties in complying with the profile and trading volumes agreed upon.
- **regulatory risk**, i.e., unforeseeable regulatory changes that can influence the value and volume of energy in the long term.

Since this is a bilateral agreement, the PPA can take several forms and can be adapted to the parts. Electricity supplies may be physical or take place through balancing groups.

PPAs are used in particular by large consumers of electricity and in the case of major investments planned for the construction or maintenance of renewable energy plants because they can reduce risks related to market prices.

PPA contracts may have different durations depending on the need of the electricity producer (annual contracts; shorter or longer formulas).

Since PPAs are bilateral contracts, then is complicated to classify them exhaustively.

A possible classification of the different types of Power Purchase Agreements is:

- 1. Physical PPA (PPA on-site; PPA off-site; Sleeved PPA).**
- 2. Synthetic PPA (or Virtual PPA).**

Several PPA schemes have been tested in Europe over the last years. The most common scheme (utility PPA) envisages as parties of the agreement a producer from renewables and a wholesale buyer (trader or utility) which buys all the electricity generated by the plant and resells it on the wholesale market. This scheme is particularly widespread in Spain, and it has been used for the first non-intragroup renewable long-term PPA in Italy (between Canadian Solar – currently, Sonnedix – and Trailstone) since it is a valid tool for the financing of renewable projects which are often developed by infrastructure funds. A more complex scheme envisages a triangulation among the producer, the wholesaler, and a corporate end customer. In this case, the wholesaler does not sell the withdrawn electricity on the market but ensures its resale through an agreement with one or possibly more end customers, which have an interest in withdrawing the energy generated by a specific plant.

PPA scheme is different in the context of self-consumption systems (individual or collective), efficient user systems and energy communities in which renewables plants are designed and financed based on the needs of the end customer on site, which sometimes is the promoter of the project itself (so-called “on-site” or “private wire” PPA). In addition to “physical” PPAs, i.e., those that envisage the supply of electricity generated by renewables, also financial contracts (contracts for differences - CfD) are widely used. In particular, these contracts protect the producer from price risks (in the event of either hedging contracts or combination of physical supply at a variable price and hedging contract) or ensure the producer a constant cash flow regardless of the meteorological risk (proxy revenues swap) leaving it solely exposed to the operational risk connected with the non-operation of the plant (the so-called “availability risk” which is, however, transferred from the producer to the contractors responsible for the construction and the maintenance of the plant).

From the point of view of the future producer, the PPA is the key to obtain bank financing that allows the construction of large-scale plants. The presence of a third party that undertakes to

purchase the energy produced by the plant, for a number of pre-established years, makes it possible to draw up the business plan, creates the possibility of meeting the instalment payments of a bank loan and thus undoubtedly raises the reliability index of the initiative.

So, in summary, Power Purchase Agreement's advantages are:

- the long-term price security.
- the possibility of financing investments in new production capacity or of reducing risks in the sale and purchase of electricity.
- the possibility of a specific electricity physical supply with certain regional characteristics and guarantees of origin. That allows customers to make their brand more sustainable and greener.

Power Purchase Agreement's disadvantages are:

- PPAs are complex contracts and often require a great deal of time and consultation before they can be successfully concluded.
- In Power Purchase Agreements both parties are bound by long-term conditions (long-term contracts).
- The production of electricity, especially wind and photovoltaic, can vary greatly. If the agreed electricity volumes are not available at the time set for supply, the plant operator shall be able to compensate them financially or physically or outsource them to third parties.

PPAs are increasingly popular in Italy, though less so than in other geographies such as the United Kingdom, Spain, Scandinavia, and the United States. The mechanisms currently in place in Italy (e.g., tax breaks and net metering) continue to support the mainstreaming of renewable energies. In addition, since the end of 2019 auctions are being used for new incentive-based RES plants. However, some sources such as wind energy and PV are becoming competitive in the market: indeed, new projects are being implemented that have been started without any incentive and several PPAs have been signed. [5]

3.2 Between service providers and the community (consumers, prosumers, industries, SMEs, ...)

One of the services that will be most in demand from the ESCO perspective for energy communities is Energy Performance Contracting (EPC). It is a form of "creative financing" for capital improvement that allows energy improvements to be financed from cost reductions. Under an EPC agreement an outside organization (e.g., ESCOs) implements a project to improve energy efficiency or renewable energy production and uses the revenue stream from cost savings or returns from the renewable energy produced to reimburse the total project costs, including those of the initial investment. Essentially, ESCOs will not receive their payment unless the project delivers energy savings as expected.

The approach is based on the transfer of technical risks from the customer to the ESCO, based on the performance guarantees given by the ESCO. In Energy Performance Contracting (EPC), the ESCO's remuneration is based on demonstrated performance; a measure of performance is, for example, the level of energy savings or the benefits of an energy service. The EPC is a means of securing infrastructure improvements for facilities that lack energy engineering expertise, manpower or management time, capital funding, understanding of risk, or technological information. Therefore, cash-strapped but creditworthy customers are good potential customers for EPC.

The three principal Energy Performance Contracting models are:

1. **Shared savings:** Under a shared savings contract the customer takes over some of the performance risk of the installed measure, so will not be responsible for the initial investment risk. The ESCO therefore assumes both performance and credit risks, securing the loan against its share of anticipated energy cost savings.
2. **Guaranteed savings:** Under a guaranteed savings contract the ESCO guarantees a certain level of energy savings thereby removing an element of performance risk for the customer but will not finance the project. Financing for such schemes is generally provided by banks or financing agencies.
3. **Chauffage:** A common contract in Europe is the 'chauffage' contract, where an ESCO takes over complete responsibility for the provision to the client of an agreed set of energy services and provides in effect an extreme form of energy management outsourcing. The ESCO takes on the responsibility for providing the agreed level of energy service for lower than the current bill or for providing improved level of service for the same bill. The more efficiently and cheaply it can do this, the greater its earnings.

Despite the large economic potential for energy savings in the EU, today very few ESCOs apply Energy Performance Contracting to the residential market due to the following main barriers that make large-scale application of the ESCO EPC model for residential buildings particularly difficult:

- High transaction costs: payback periods under EPC contracts are not attractive.
- High market fragmentation: there is a huge population of buildings characterized by the availability of a variety of technologies and installed devices that are either not connected or - this is the case for "smart" devices - the diversity of communication protocols and the lack of clear standardization guidelines considerably increase the complexity of data collection and management functions.
- The landlord/tenant dilemma: the landlord has no economic motivation to reduce electricity costs, which are paid by tenants, making investments unattractive and the payback periods considerably high.
- Variation in individual needs and behaviours that require personalized treatment when it comes to energy management to avoid disruptions in daily life and degradation of living standards.
- Lack of information and expertise at the residential consumer level in EPC and energy management and reluctance to engage in constant interaction with home systems and service providers to maximize energy benefits.
- Fear of relying on specific contractors for a long period.
- Inability of tenants/household owners to cope with upfront investments (if necessary) and lack of public subsidies and per capita funding, especially considering the low attractiveness of typical EPC schemes and services.

Therefore, new EPC contracts should decouple from current savings-based performance contracts and allow for adaptation to evolving energy market trends with the introduction of novel hybrid schemes that not only reduce costs, but also create new revenue streams for end consumers/prosumers, empowering them to participate in energy transactions and become active players.

This approach is expected to significantly reduce the payback period for relevant investments in smart equipment, resources, and distributed energy assets (e.g., storage, electric vehicles), thus increasing the attractiveness of modern Energy Performance Contracts for both the investor (ESCO/aggregator) and the consumer (also enabling the elimination of the tenant/landlord dilemma).

The star idea on the adaptation of ESCOs to the new landscape would be the generation of the next generation of EPCs on the basis of synergistic business models between aggregators and ESCOs, innovative hybrid energy services that properly combine energy efficiency and demand

response, clear and well specified legal/contractual provisions and objective measurement and verification schemes to ensure objective verification of savings and fair and transparent remuneration of flexibility according to the principles of pay-for-performance schemes.

4 Arrangement strategies

Energy communities offer multiple benefits, as they can provide flexibility and, when connected to the main energy system, increase the reliability and resilience of the entire system. Today there are numerous success stories of energy communities, and the use of batteries and demand aggregators are tools with which citizens can accelerate the transition to a healthier (decarbonized) and cheaper energy model. Therefore, it is essential to adapt the grid and the Energy Service Operators (ESOs) to the new paradigm that is coming.

Indeed, a flexible system able to adapt to the variability characteristic of wind and solar photovoltaic energies is needed as wind does not always blow when we need it, and the sun does not always shine when we need it. According to the International Renewable Energy Agency (Irena), flexibility is "the ability of an energy system to cope with the variability and uncertainty introduced by solar and wind energy on different time scales, from the very short to the long term, minimizing the discharges of these variable renewable energy sources and reliably supplying all customers' energy demand". Flexibility is what the end user of energy can bring through their ability to manage their own demand.

The transition in which we are immersed presents a major challenge: how to "absolutely" integrate renewable energies and other clean technologies into the energy sector while guaranteeing the stability of the grid and energy supply. And the key to this is flexibility.

Three main mechanisms have been identified for the user to be an enabler of this flexibility: self-consumption, storage, and demand aggregator.

- **Self-consumption:** the consumer has the capacity to generate his own energy to reduce the demand dependent on the national generation park. Self-consumption not only involves reducing consumer demand on the overall system, but also allows surplus energy to be shared with others (through energy communities) or fed into the grid, also contributing to national generation.
- **Storage:** these systems will be relevant in consumer empowerment and demand management since, on the one hand, they boost self-consumption by allowing the storage of surplus energy from renewable sources and, on the other hand, they allow the consumption of electrified services.
- **Demand manager or aggregator:** this regulated actor is set to be decisive, so that consumers can take a step forward in regulating their consumption and obtain some kind

of benefit in return, from simply achieving savings on their electricity bill to the limit of actively participating, through a third party, in the electricity markets.

The *independent aggregator* is the market participant that provides aggregation services and is not related to the customer's supplier, i.e., to the marketing activity, being therefore an independent figure. The EU's ultimate objective with the definition of this figure and its operational framework is to enable independent aggregators to perform their role as intermediaries and thus ensure that the end user (industrial, commercial, and domestic) benefits adequately from their activities. The European Union specifies that all user groups must have access to electricity markets to trade their flexibility and self-generated electricity or do so on an aggregated basis through a demand aggregator. To this end, it must ensure that Member States allow and encourage the participation of demand response through aggregation in electricity markets, imposing a series of requirements to ensure the rights and obligations of participants (transparent rules on the roles and responsibilities of such participants, non-discriminatory and transparent procedures for the exchange of information between them or financial responsibility for the deviations they cause in the electricity system) and a series of rights on the final consumer (right to change supplier, freedom to buy and sell electricity services, right to receive their demand response data, ...).

The demand aggregator will be greatly enhanced and benefited by new technologies and digitization, as they will enable it to group together different players in the sector in the same energy subsystem (consumers, small producers, prosumers, batteries, electric vehicle charging points, etc.). With these agents grouped together, the objective is to aggregate and combine the multiple consumption and production of electricity for its efficient sale and purchase on the electricity production market. Aggregators enter into a contractual agreement with consumers and generally operate a large number of distributed energy resources of different types, or they can also specialize in a particular type of resource, such as behind-the-meter storage systems. Thus, through so-called virtual power plants (VPPs), aggregators can sell electricity in electricity markets or provide flexibility services to the system.

For improving the energy efficiency, a 'right' mix of policies (as discussed in previous sections), technologies and behavioural changes is needed. Hence, this chapter discusses first the approaches and suitable means that influence the user behaviour, and then presents how the corresponding business models might be supported in practice from social, financial, and technical viewpoints.

4.1 Identification of suitable means how to influence user behaviour

In order to reveal and propose strategic means to understand and shift end-users' behaviours, methods from Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) will be employed. These methodologies are key to comprehend the needs, perceptions and day to day practices related to energy, as well as propose behavioural changes to increase energy efficiency. For such, different steps are proposed **First step:** conducting in-depth interviews will allow to identify what do end-users know and how they perceive their energy practices. In Deliverable 1.2, interviews were conducted to all stakeholders of the CEC's, yielding relevant insights about their pain points, opportunities, and potentialities in the behavioural dimension of energy efficiency.

Second step: disseminating a questionnaire to further delve into the tacit knowledge and concrete knowledge, dwellings conditions and energy practices. In Deliverable 1.4, different end-users answered a questionnaire that led to understanding key end-user requirements and possibilities for energy efficiency.

Third step: Consolidate arrangement strategies based on the inputs of the interviews and questionnaire answers, in order to raise energy use awareness and propose a cultural shift. In Deliverable, several end-user needs were identified in terms of community dynamics: promoting a better understanding of energy bills and energy behavioural changes, improving decision-making about energy self-sufficiency, gaining transparency of the contracts and data usage, promoting the use of public transport where available, and educating people about the benefits of electrical vehicles. To approach these, at this stage, different means are to be explored:

- **Communication means:** written and audio-visual materials are key to promote easy to understand, powerful pills of information about energy efficiency. Different formats (such as radio, online and paper news, TV, etc.) will allow adapting the message to different formats, generations, and end-users.
- **Formal training:** formal sessions of training about technical and social aspects of energy can be valuable for those end-users that are more motivated and willing to “study” about it.
- **Community driven shared learnings:** in CECs an enriching way of learning is through end-users' sharing of experiences to maximise their energy efficiency. To stimulate it, games and in person activities and workshops are an asset. In this sense, some facilitation tools can be valuable, as follows:
 - o **Future scenario:** in groups, envisioning future scenarios of energy efficiency can help end-users propose creative ways of engaging in new behaviours in terms of appliances use, time sensitivity and even decision making around renovation works.

- Graphic facilitation: using visual tools (images, drawings, maps and other graphic elements) are useful to transmit, produce and collaboratively analyse ideas within a focused group of people. These workshops take advantage of collective intelligence to seek alternatives and generate proposals about key challenges such as democratisation and decentralisation of energy in a city of building block. Graphic facilitation techniques are procedures that explore the evocative and triggering capacity of graphic tools and actions surrounding them.
- **App induced**: the app is also a great tool to engage end-users in new practices and pave the way towards a shift in the way they perceive energy production and energy usage. In Deliverable 1.4, driving end-user requirements were revealed in terms of technologies: tracking economic and environmental savings, tips for demand-side flexibility and to reduce energy consumption, and making available easy to understand daily and hourly information about energy production and consumption. To tackle these requirements through the NEON app, the gamification of the app and pieces of information it puts forward will be crucial to raise awareness and engage end-users.

These means to influence user behaviour fit directly into the engagement strategies designed for each CEC in D 1.4. They are meant to tackle the sociocultural dimension of energy, in order to enable a transition of end-users from passive to active, informed, and critical users of energy. This sociocultural change takes time, and the innovation of technological but also community-driven processes.

4.2 Putting arrangements and business models in practice

4.2.1 Organisation among CEC's members

The members inside an Energy Community can be classified into 3 different types, consumers, prosumers, and producers/investors. Depending on the type of stakeholder their arrangements with the community will be different according to their characteristics.

- **Consumers**: This category includes any of the members who do not have a production system to generate energy into the community, this will help define their arrangements because there will be no more than two values to control. For these stakeholders, the principal measures to control will be the energy consumed and when is this energy consumed (E(Wh), T(hour.) ;).

Inside this category there will be, final residential end users which will use energy in their normal daily lives, enterprises which will consume energy during their work process and different **service providers** which will consume energy to bring the people their services.

- **Prosumers:** This category includes members who are able to produce energy and also consume it at the same time. For example, a business that has its own generation installation and can be considered an end-user can be in this category.

In order to perform agreements with these types of members it will be necessary to be able to control more information values as the energy generated, the energy consumed and the moment when this energy its generated. (Egen(Wh), Econ(Wh), T(hour) ;).

- **Investors:** This category includes any member of the community who, for the formation of the community, must make a financial contribution at the beginning of the community. This does not include members who join the community or who are required to make an initial payment to join the community, regardless of whether it is for the purchase of equipment or membership fees.

The community will have representative figures for each type of member and every representative figure will participate to regular meetings to analyse the results of the energy community and their collective. There will be one representative elected in each group of stakeholders, and a main manager which will be normally, the promoter of the pilot.

Figure 2 Assembly of representative of each figure

The final end-users will need to elect a representative who must also be a member of the group which it represents and of course, part of the community. Those representatives will be elected considering the gender parity to guarantee equal opportunity for both genders.

At these meetings, the progress achieved within the community will be evaluated in general terms as well as for each of the groups. With the data obtained, it will be possible to modify or not the conditions of each member or group of members in a way that is not only beneficial for them but for the group of members.

Figure 3 Organisational scheme within the Energy community

After each meeting it will be necessary to make a summary of the meeting in which the deviations to be solved for each group within the community are established. To this end, minutes will be drawn up and signed by each member of the meeting. These minutes will contain the information provided by each representative as well as the solutions or changes foreseen for future actions within the community.

These minutes will have a public character and can be consulted by each of the members at any time, thus being informed of the actions and progress made within the community.

All these actions or measures adopted in the meetings held by the community members will be carried out, for the most part, on the contracts of the community members.

At this point, it will be of great importance the definition of contracts such as P4P and EPC, which may be established as dynamic contracts, varying their conditions according to what is agreed upon by the representative parties in the different assemblies, being the modifications notified to all the members of the community.

Given that each community will be based on a different type of economic model, the agreements within each community will be based on the economic nature of the community, and reference can be made within the document itself, if necessary.

Within each contract modality, there will be a series of conditions that will be defined by an internal P4P programme, which will generate retributions or discounts on members' consumption as well as improvements based on their availability for changes and ease of power treatment.

The contracts must also consider minimum requirements for the fulfilment of the conditions assigned to the members of the community, some of which are set out below:

- Each contract must clearly determine to which modality the member belongs.
- Power required defined by periods.
- Hourly energy price (both to be consumed and to be injected). These prices will be a reflection of where the energy came from, being the energy consumed directly from the PV installation the cheapest one.
- Incentives for modifying consumptions patterns or by acting over consumptions from the NEON platform.
- Penalties for unforeseen excessive consumption.
- Penalties for lack of production or availability of energy storage due to lack of foresight or lack of maintenance.
- Technical aspects that members will be able to consult on the NEON platform according to their membership. This part should include some data or statistics about the self-consumption ratio, kWh used from the storage system, or the number of kWh consumed from the EV charging point and how many of those have been consumed from renewable sources.
- A certain amount of money should be earmarked for the maintenance of the staff that will control the technical aspects of the community.
- The contracts shall clearly define the sections referring to EPCs and P4Ps, and what the terms of these are.
- As in any contract, it will also be necessary to establish a minimum period of permanence in the community in order to guarantee the income corresponding to the associated management and personnel costs.
- Minimum participation required of community members.
- Establish the frequency of meetings.

Each contract will have particular terms and conditions depending on its energy community, so the members of the community and their nature will be a determining factor when establishing

internal agreements. They will also affect each community's own objectives, so that agreements will be different for situations that are the same but pursue different objectives.

4.2.2 Financial and legal ecosystem

While the European Union is experiencing an unprecedented crisis, caused by the climate change and a geopolitical, economic, and social instability, the coordination of various stakeholders within the setting of energy communities can overcome some of the main problems and bring numerous benefits to all involved in, creating greater local resilience (both socially and economical). In particular, renewable energy communities can experience costs' reduction, incomes' generation, and stability of the prices of energy and related services by two factors: **self-organization** and **decentralization**. That is because decentralized communities are built around local suppliers and provide customers with more stable and comparatively cheaper energy prices. The key lies in long-term contractual arrangements with fixed prices that do not necessarily reflect market prices [4]

Under the Electricity Directive EU 2019/944 within the Clean Energy Package (CEP), energy communities are considered legal persons allowed to operate power plants and consume the generated energy among the members; alternatively, energy communities can supply external customers (through PPA) or opt for feed-in quotas (see D2.1 - "Legal and financial framework for cross-service integration"). Given their focus on local and renewable self-consumption, energy communities could detach their price calculations from market prices because energy communities are not considered suppliers and hence not bound to follow the merit-order principle that governs the current market design. Rather, they can set up tariff schemes for their members and/or external customers (non-members of the energy community) and these prices might be stable compared to fluctuating market prices.

The stability of energy prices is one of the most important aspects for citizens participating in pilot CEC of NEON project (see D1.2 - "Service offer Co-creation and business planning"). The conclusions of Deliverable 1.2 show that involved stakeholders perceived the arising opportunities regarding an empowerment of an Energy Community to face and mitigate the effect of surging energy costs and linked increase in their domestic energy bills. The formation of the energy community was considered crucial to become independent from the local energy provider and lower the risk generated by energy dependency from the national grid, in addition to the fact that NEON can play a crucial role for the reduction of a potential additional installation costs connected to the new installations and guaranteeing an overall return of investment to generate an advantage to CEC's members.

These benefits might not only be enjoyed by the members of the community themselves. Rather, power-purchase agreements (see section 3.1, p. 28) with external customers might turn out as a practical instrument that provides energy communities with an income, while customers enjoy stable and secure energy prices. The legal idea of power-purchase agreements allows for various corollaries. On the one hand, consumers who cannot participate in energy communities could enter into power-purchase agreements with the energy community. Further, non-SME businesses might rent rooftop space to energy communities for the installation of PV. And if the available space allows for enough production capacity, these businesses could enter power-purchase agreements with energy communities. Thereby, contractual instruments such as fair-use clauses might provide against the over-consumption of one community member or external customer. From EU Electricity Directive 2019/944 it follows that earned profits should not be distributed to shareholders but re-invested in the community, thereby bound to certain (contractually) well-defined community centred. Exemplarily, the energy community could invest in power to heat solutions, charging stations and other innovative services.

In general, the contractual practice allows for various combinations of production and consumption that complement each other: this is to say that the mere vicinity of different members of an energy community might not make them the best match available from an economic point of view. Rather, different load profiles must be combined to balance production, storage, and consumption. Thus, energy communities might benefit from diverse membership (businesses, municipal buildings, private houses, civil society organizations such as churches, etc.) with varying load profiles and (rooftop) generation capacities.

By installing local generation capacities, energy communities are a further step closer to decentralized energy production and consumption. They might help decrease the cost-intensive need for regional, national, and cross-border grid expansion as foreseen for the intercontinental transport of power.

4.2.3 Technical implementation aspects of cross-sectoral arrangements

4.2.3.1 Pre-conditions for connected communities

The transition to a more integrated energy system is of crucial importance for Europe. Hence novel sensors, advanced data exchange infrastructures, and data handling capabilities that make use of Big Data, Artificial Intelligence, 5G and distributed ledger technologies are needed to enhance forecasting, allow the remote monitoring and management of distributed generation and improve asset optimisation. The pre-conditions for connected communities and deployment

of AI solutions for energy efficiency and demand-side optimization can be discussed from following viewpoints

- Smart Grids, Power System Digitalization and Automation,
- Data exchange, Orchestration, ICT Interoperability, Standardization viewpoint (Reference architectures and Common Information Models),
- Big data and Analytics services for smart energy management

NEON aims to enable the technical and business ecosystem of integrated energy services for energy communities located in the European territory. Having as a basic principle of integration both energy efficiency and demand, these integrated services aim at better energy management and minimization of energy consumption, reducing greenhouse gas emissions, and have a democratic social and economic basis.

4.2.3.2 Smart grids, power system digitalization and automation

The smart grid approach usually leads to an increased level of complexity of system operation and control. This also requires distributed intelligence on different levels in the system. The different levels of intelligence applied to smart grid systems can be categorized as follows [6]:

- *System level:* Approaches like power utility automation, demand-side management or energy management are tackled by this level.
- *Sub-system level:* The optimization and the control of sub-systems are carried out below the system level whereas the corresponding functions, services, and algorithms have to deal with a limited number of components (RES, energy storage system, electric vehicle supply equipment, etc.). Examples for this level are micro-grid control approaches and home/building energy management concepts.
- *Component level:* Distributed Energy Resources (DER)/RES, distributed energy storage systems but also electric vehicle supply equipment is covered by this layer.
- *Sub-component level:* Intelligence on this level is mainly used to improve the local component behaviour/properties (harmonics, flicker, etc.). Power electronics (and their advanced control algorithms) are the main driver for local intelligence on this level. The development of the smart grid brought many new applications (distributed automation / generation / storage, automated demand response, etc.) that are distributed by nature, and which operate on top of communication infrastructures. To address the growing demand for communication due to the various new smart grid applications as well as for economic reasons, utilities need to move away from purpose-built networks and consolidate communication in integrated smart grid communication architecture.

The high-level architecture of a smart community includes:

- Electricity generation devices (RES plants, Hydrogen power plants).
- office and residential buildings.
- storage devices.
- control centre for data acquisition, exchange, control, and automation.

Figure 4 below presents, for instance, the smart energy community ecosystem that is built from actors (platforms) that are geographically displaced, however connected, and orchestrated. **Edge/cloud orchestration mechanisms** have to be put in place to manage the multi-cloud/edge and federated environments. The NEON reference architecture for achieving orchestration on different levels in the NEON ecosystem has been discussed in D1.5.

Figure 4 Example of Smart community

4.2.3.3 Data exchange and orchestration

The primary CEC goal is to improve self-consumption while targeting cost savings, resiliency, quality of service, system performance, responsiveness, and contributions to municipalities and the surrounding communities. The data acquisition and exchange mechanisms in cross-sectoral arrangements depend on the type and number of involved parties (stakeholders, control and automation services/systems, market related services). In general, the CEC infrastructure (renewable energy installations, electric vehicle charging stations, etc.) is owned by the CEC as a legal entity, while the provided (energy efficiency, flexibility) services are provided by ESCo. Hence, ESCo needs different technological instruments (supporting infrastructure) to ensure:

- interaction among actors (platforms) within the community,

- data acquisition (sensors),
- implementation of control mechanisms (generation and consumption devices),
- interaction with actors (platforms) outside the community.

An example of data exchange needs for the CEC-3 is illustrated in the Figure 5 below.

Figure 5 Example of Stakeholders interaction schema (CEC 3)

To fully achieve the benefits of smart grid, a range of new software applications, components, and improvements to business processes will rely on information emanating from existing and new systems and data sources. These new smart software components will need to interpret business semantics in a common way in order to ensure that data can be exchanged and shared, and that business intelligence activities can be carried out in an efficient and cost-effective manner. An open, and shared information model provides such common semantics.

EU foresees transformation of existing industry value chain processes, introduction of intermediaries and marketplaces, introduction of SOA platforms that address both dimensions of change integrated business processes supported by cross-functional teams; and integrated tools along the entire value chain that enable the processes.

Several initiatives have been proposed to develop effective and scalable semantic interoperability towards data spaces. In the context of the European Data Strategy [7] and the proposed Regulation on European Data Governance [8], a vision has been created for trusted data intermediaries for B2B data sharing and common European data spaces, as well as for promoting advanced energy services via a marketplace. Adopting semantic interoperability solutions, various interconnected systems and data sources will be described using a common representation language, thus achieving a unified access to the available data.

4.2.3.4 Smart energy management services

Key factors in providing self-sustainability and increasing energy efficiency in CEC electric power grids are the optimal utilization of locally available clean renewable energy in accordance with the appropriate potentials of each RES plant and community involvement through participation in interactive load management and demand response (DR) programmes [9]. With these two combined, they would unlock a certain flexibility from the demand side and allow for the demand to be moulded and adjusted to match the intermittent profile of generation typical for contemporary renewable energy sources as a result of their dependency on uncontrollable meteorological (photovoltaic panels, wind turbines, wave generators) and geological conditions (geothermal production sources). With demand-side flexibility provided by end users, optimization algorithms can be utilized in order to provide the best match between supply and demand in order to minimize the costs of running the (energy) system and maximize the exploitation of locally available renewable sources. With minor modifications, such algorithms can also be employed in cases where storage systems are present and used to monitor a wide variety of economic factors as well as indicators of grid stability which could be used as key performance indicators that should be managed in high renewable penetration systems.

In Task 1.5 framework, the proposed NEON project reference architecture the following types of analytical services

- Energy production and energy demand data analytics (see Task 3.1).
- Digital control algorithms (see Task 3.2).
- Energy Hub concept for optimal energy asset (RES, storage, EVs) scheduling (see Task 3.3).
- User-tailored services and non-energy benefits bundling (see Task 3.4).
- Hybrid DR mechanisms based on multiple interconnected Energy Hubs (see Task 3.5).

Examples of services are given in D1.5 NEON platform architecture and performance assessment KPIs.

5 Specific cross-sectoral arrangements for NEON’s CECs

Energy communities, according to the Clean Energy Package (CEP)¹, “provide for organisational frameworks for collective energy initiatives, which have new possibilities to act in the energy sector, including new rights to access the energy markets.” [10]

Depending on the countries and the level of transposition of EU legislation into national legislation, energy communities vary [11]in:

- Size – depending on the number of customers involved in self-consumption.
- Portfolio – depending on type of services (generation, distribution, or also serving as balance responsible party and offering flexibility to system operators)
- Infrastructure – with or without grid ownership.
- Market model – aimed for the actors within the community or also interacting with other markets.

Hence, depending on the goals, different paths (projects, actors) shall be selected (initiated, engaged) for the establishment of a Citizen Energy Community.

NEON Project pre-selected the following four citizen energy communities (CECs) categorised in Table 2 to serve as early adopters and to provide adequate testbed for identification and showcase of NEON service concepts and business models.

Table 2 Categorization of NEON CECs

CEC	CEC-01- Berchidda (IT)	CEC-02: DOMAINE DE LA SOURCE (FR)	CEC-03: POLIGONO INDUSTRIAL LAS CABEZAS (ES)	CEC-04: STAIN CITY (FR)
Size	Municipality	Residential buildings	Industrial and residential building	2 buildings/sites
Portfolio	Different services running on their platform	Different services running on their platform	NEON Platform considered to be deployed	Different services running on their platform
Infrastructure	Municipality serves as DSO	ALB acts as ESCo	GFM – energy provider and ESCo	Part of larger CEC
Market Model	EPC and P4P contracting	EPC and P4P contracting	P2P energy trading	EPC contractual arrangements

In this Chapter 5, possible cross-sectoral arrangements are assessed for each energy service identified in each CEC in task T1.1 and each stakeholder interviewed in T1.2 in order to analyse their possible deployment considering user requirements, relevant grid aspects, and links to the building efficiency retrofit. The strategies analysed in the previous section are here tailored and

adapted to the specific CECs involved in NEON project by analysing the suitable means to influence the user behaviour and how the business models will be supported in practice specifically in each CEC involved in NEON's Project.

5.1 CEC01 - Location: BERCHIDDA, Berchidda Municipality, Italy

Berchidda is a village located on the southern slopes of Mount Limbara, in the north of Sardinia Island with a population of approximately 3,000 inhabitants. The land covers approx. 201km² and it is located at an average altitude of 300 m. The anthropic structures, vegetation and climatic conditions are typical for the inland areas of Sardinia, with average temperatures of 15°C.

The CEC will be comprised of residential, commercial, and public buildings (e.g., municipality, school, recreation centre). Part of them only consumers and part of them prosumers with a private PV system on their roofs. The city counts up to today 62 private PV systems (800kWp in total) and an energy production of about 820MWh (so 14% RES share), and three municipal (220kWp) and two industrial (130kWp) PV plants.

Since January 2021, the Municipality is officially owner of its electricity grid, both town centre and surrounding rural area, and it serves as DSO in form of AEC (Azienda Elettrica Comunale - Municipality electricity company of Berchidda).

As defined in D1.2. "Service offer co-creation and business planning", and agreed with the CEC stakeholders, Berchidda will be engaged in setting up two main services: (1) Local Energy Community Building (see Table 3) and (2) PV collective-self- consumption (see Table 4).

The Italian pilot involves the following main stakeholders in the setup of the Berchidda's CEC and the implementation of the energy services identified in D1.1:

GRIDABILITY: As pilot coordinator, citizen engagement; interface with the municipality; blockchain-based platform and automated smart DR settlement; installation of smart meters.

ENERGY4COM: an Italian cooperative startup that will support the Municipality in creating the local energy community. It partners already with GridAbility.

R2M ENERGY (ESCO): As Gridability's LTP, it will support it in the demonstration actions at Berchidda's CEC and play the role of Energy Manager who will advise and organise strategies for RES penetration and energy efficiency to be implemented in the pilot. Being an ESCo it will also deal with energy contract negotiations to encourage the use of renewable and sustainable energy resources and innovative highly efficient technologies.

AEC (DSO): the Municipality electricity company of Berchidda, that is owned by the Municipality that thus has a double role of grid operator and DSO, and of public administration representing the citizens. AEC is not a separate legal entity: it is a department of the Municipality. The engagement of the Municipality's technical office is crucial for the technical installations; the

engagement of the mayor and his staff is essential in motivating the citizens to participate in the EU projects (like HESTIA, LocalRES, NEON), to disseminate basic information about energy and demand response, and to ensure a long-term engagement of the citizens.

CITIZENS, LOCAL INDUSTRIES AND SMEs (END USERS): they are the primary beneficiary of the Berchidda Smart Grid 4.0 and the key actor in enhancing demand response and adjusting their energy behaviours and consumption to reach the communities’ objectives. Berchidda inhabitants will be addressed with general communications to improve the adoption of the innovative solutions and increase the number of members of the energy community in the long run.

Table 3 Cross sectoral arrangement for Local Energy Community service in CEC-01

Energy Service	Local Energy Community					
Stakeholders	Grid stakeholder (DSO - AEC)	Cooperative (Energy4Com)	Prosumers End-Users (Residential and Industrial – Giogantinu Winery and Cork Industry Colla & Fresu)	Only Consumers End-Users (Residential and industrial – Berchidda’s citizens)	ESCo (R2M Energy)	Service Provider (AXPO)
Arrangements	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Creation of Berchidda’s REC 2. Energy efficiency survey (e.g., Energy audit) 3. Metering and monitoring services for energy management 4. EPC contracts for Solar systems (PV/Solar Thermal) and for building’s Heating and Cooling system renovation and optimization 5. EV charging stations 6. Training and dissemination 					
Description of the arrangement	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Creation of Berchidda’s REC Energy4Com supported by Gridability and R2M Energy is guiding Berchidda’s Municipality and its citizens through the legal creation of their local REC. Social engagement and energy awareness will be set up among Berchidda’s residents that want to engage into behavioural change and citizen community engagement. Members of the community (consumers, prosumers, investors) will also be able to exploit the national incentives for REC’s creation allocated by the Italian government. 2. Energy efficiency survey (e.g., Energy audit) R2M Energy will play the role of Energy manager in CEC-01 and offer to the community its expertise in the energy efficiency retrofit and energy management fields. R2M Energy will perform inspection surveys in the community’s buildings to analyse their energy consumption and propose alternative scenarios of renovation to reduce their energy expense and carbon footprint. (Baseline definition and Energy retrofit scenarios) 3. Metering and monitoring services for energy management The Municipality of Berchidda owns its electricity network in the form of AEC (Azienda Elettrica Comunale – Municipal Electricity Company) and decided to upgrade it with the 					

	<p>project Berchidda Energy 4.0 smart grid in which it plans to deploy 400 NesosNet smart meters to gather the city's buildings energy data. The energy metering and monitoring will allow to implement an energy management system and/or to evaluate the benefits of potential energy efficiency investments. (Check of energy efficiency scenarios)</p> <p>4. EPC contracts for Solar systems (PV/Solar Thermal) and for building's Heating and Cooling system renovation and optimization</p> <p>As part of the energy efficiency services that will be deployed within Berchidda CEC, new heat pump systems will be installed in residential buildings. They will be mainly electrical air-to-air heat pump system that will replace existing older heating and cooling gas systems so as to improve the energy efficiency and performance of the buildings and reduce the carbon emissions in the energy system. They will all be equipped with a monitoring and control system, allowing the end-user to increase its energy consumption awareness in one hand and for the prosumers to control and match their consumption with their PV system's production. R2M Energy will also enhance RES penetration by negotiating EPC contracts for PV systems and Solar thermal systems with the members of the community. (Technical economical proposal of energy efficiency solutions)</p> <p>5. EV charging stations</p> <p>Berchidda will add value to its city by installing EV charging stations in strategic points of the town to attract more tourists and serve as intermediate point to two main tourist areas of North Sardinia. R2M Energy worked closely with the Municipality to define the points where to install them and for the connections permit as it is also the DSO of the city's grid. The EV charging service will be provided by AXPO through prepaid energy service, and potential agreements with rental airport companies, recurring services or cultural events are under evaluation.</p> <p>6. Training and dissemination</p> <p>The pilot coordinator (Gridability) along with the energy manager experts (R2M Energy) will organise with the help of the Municipality a serie of conference, seminars, workshops, as well as teaching activities to engage citizens in the CEC and to increase their awareness in terms of energy consumption, renewable sources and energy control and management systems.</p>
User requirements	Sense of community and collaboration, and willingness to participate actively in the community's energy transition and common benefits.
Technical requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Presence of RES: As of today in Italy, it is only possible to create a REC and not a CEC, the presence of renewable energy production plants within the EC is mandatory - Smart meters in all the buildings of the community
Law Reference / Legislation	Currently, the Italian legislation on renewable energy communities consists of Article 42-bis of the Milleproroghe Decree 162/2019 (converted by Law no. 8/2020 of 28 February 2020), the relevant implementing measures (ARERA's Resolution 318/2020/R/eel and the DM of 16 September 2020 of the MiSE) and Legislative Decree 199 of 8 November 2021 , which implements the European RED II Directive on the promotion of the use of energy from renewable sources.
Main Barriers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Long and complicated legal bureaucracy for the formalisation of the REC

Grid Relevant aspects	Maximum installed power 1MW/plant, under the same medium voltage station.
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Table 4 Cross sectoral arrangement Collective Self-consumption from PV production service in CEC-01

Energy Service	Collective self-consumption PV production			
Stakeholders	Grid stakeholder (DSO - AEC)	Cooperative (Energy4Com)	Prosumers End-Users (Residential and Industrial – Giogantinu Winery and Cork Industry Colla & Fresu)	Only Consumers End-Users (Residential and industrial – Berchidda’s citizens)
Arrangements	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. PV-Self Consumption 2. Load shifting with BESS 3. P4P Pay for Performance - Share of renewable energy value among CEC’s members 			
Description of the arrangement	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. PV-Self Consumption Maximise the share of renewable sources of energy usage produced locally within the REC by matching on an hourly balance the PV production with the building’s consumption to value the energy consumed and produced with the national incentive for RES self-consumption that allocates around 160Euro (according to fluctuating national energy price) per MWh self-produced and self-consumed in the same hour. Among other benefits this will allow to reduce the energy import from the grid bringing both environmental (reduction of CO2 emissions) and economic benefits (energy bill reduction). 2. Load shifting with BESS In order to increase even more the benefits of the REC and take advantage of the national incentive, the energy that is locally produced by the PV systems within the REC and not used to cover the REC member’s consumption will be stored in BESS during the day so as to use it during the night when there is no PV production that could be used directly to cover the building’s consumption. This will allow to reduce the import of energy from the grid and reduce the end-user’s energy bill, and it will avoid feeding the surplus of renewable energy produced by the PV system into the grid locally, which would be repaid at a much lower price than the purchase price. It is therefore more profitable to match one’s consumption with the PV production curve than to sell the surplus to the grid at a low price and buy it back at a much higher price later. 3. P4P Pay for Performance - Share of renewable energy value among CEC’s members Community’s members that individually own and manage Distributed Energy Resources self-generate energy that in a “sandbox environment” they can trade locally with other members of the community. Prosumers can share their energy surplus value within the community. For this process to work, specific contract methods have to be defined and tested starting with standard EPC (Energy Performance Contracts) and moving to a better P4P (Pay for Performance mechanism) depending on CEC governance rules that will be 			

	defined. This will benefit the CEC in terms of economic gains as it will allow to increase the total share of self-consumed energy at community level that is economically valued by the Italian incentive and of reduced costs of energy dispatching based on local efficiency gains.
User requirements	Necessary and sufficient condition, the simultaneous presence within the community of prosumer profiles with private PV systems and consumer profiles. Indeed, in order to be able to value the renewable energy produced by the local PV systems with the national incentive, this energy needs to be self-consumed within the REC in the following hour otherwise this energy will only be fed into the grid at a much lower price than the purchase price. The members of the REC must know how the PV system's production trends work and be aware of their consumption's profiles in order to understand how the energy balance/matching work and how they can influence it with their habits.
Technical requirements	Necessary and sufficient metering system for hourly measurement and validation of energy fed into and withdrawn from the grid, and monitoring system suitable for the user to enable active and informed participation.
Law Reference / Legislation	Currently, the Italian legislation on renewable energy communities consists of Article 42-bis of the Milleproroghe Decree 162/2019 (converted by Law no. 8/2020 of 28 February 2020), the relevant implementing measures (ARERA's Resolution 318/2020/R/eel and the DM of 16 September 2020 of the MiSE) and Legislative Decree 199 of 8/11/2021 , which implements the European RED II Directive on the promotion of the use of energy from renewable sources.
Main Barriers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Technical/legal barrier: Maximum installed power 1MW/plant, under the same medium voltage station - Social barrier: Raise awareness and engagement. Make citizens understand the mechanisms of energy flows and the benefits that the REC can bring to them by putting them in the centre of it and in control of it.
Grid relevant aspects	Maximum installed power 1MW/plant, under the same medium voltage station.

Building energy efficiency retrofit, RES penetration and Energy systems flexibility will be enhanced in Berchidda Municipality with the creation of its CEC. The Municipality owns the electric grid and acts as DSO (in the form of AEC) and it will take advantage of the distributed energy resources (PV systems, battery storage systems installed with the HESTIA project, highly efficient electric heat pumps installed with the LocalRES project) to increase the network flexibility with the use of smart meters and energy management platform, and to enhance demand response mechanisms aimed at improving the grid stability, reducing grid exchange and decarbonizing the local energy system.

Indeed, the Municipality has conducted a recruiting campaign of the citizens to join the CEC with the guidance of the cooperative Energy4Com. Not only prosumers were targeted but also ordinary consumers that will remain as such and consumers that showed their interest in equipping their house with a PV system and are being supported by R2M Energy on that. Above these private investments also major projects of the Municipality for the installation of a

centralised PV plant and a 60kWp wind turbine are under evaluation to increase the local production of energy from renewable sources to cover the city's electricity demand.

Among the other actions and energy services that will be deployed, there is the installation of heat pumps conducted by R2M Energy with the LocalRES project to cover the heating and cooling demand of part of the members of the community coupled with the monitoring and control devices, and the smart meters will help improve the management of the community's thermal and electrical energy demand. Indeed, R2M Energy will also play the role of Energy Manager of the CEC by advising and organizing strategies to improve the energy efficiency of the buildings involved and propose sustainable alternatives of retrofit with the aim of increasing awareness and enabling energy and economical savings maintaining (or even improving) health, safety and comfort conditions. To do so, R2M Energy will conduct site inspection and surveys, collect energy data, develop strategies to reduce energy consumption with the use of renewables and negotiate energy contracts with contractors and stakeholders.

Once Berchidda CEC will be legally constituted they will identify their Community Manager that will be the main contact between the Municipality, the citizens and the different outside stakeholders to coordinate the actions and interventions inside the community. It will also be the contact person for arrangements with the pilot coordinator (Gridability) for NEON project-related activities.

From an operational point of view, the Community Manager will be responsible for the recruitment of members from a social point of view by organizing training and dissemination events to engage the citizens in the community and by disseminating communications (social media, newspaper articles, local posters in the main square, etc.), and for the onboarding of the members from a bureaucratic stand point.

The work of the Community Manager will be eased by the NesosNet Platform for monitoring purposes and by the PROSUME SaaS Platform for governance purposes.

The NesosNet platform will manage the metering data collection of the smart meters installed in the community's buildings. Data will range from environmental measures as the internal temperature to monitor the resident's comfort or optimize the thermal system operation, to measures of the assets installed like the electricity production or consumption to manage the energy fluxes inside the community. The data are then sent to the cloud for remote real-time monitoring and control, data processing and forecasting for optimization purposes.

Whereas PROSUME is extending their SaaS platform for automated billing and payment of the governmental incentives based on the rules established by the community. The Platform will integrate the Community Manager Dashboard (that allows to monitor the electricity consumption/production flows and compared to the billing flows), the Community Manager

Wallet (linked to the Community's Bank) and the Prosumer APP wallet for the end user (consumers and prosumers in general).

Moreover, it will provide a user-friendly APP to the members of the community that will be able to monitor their energy and economic flows through a digital Wallet. The end-users will increase their awareness thanks to it and be able to understand how to change their usual habits of consumption to reduce their energy bills and increase the collective share of self-consumed renewable energy that is incentivized on a daily basis.

5.2 CEC02 - Location : DOMAINE DE LA SOURCE, Villard de Lans, France

Domaine de la Source is a 25-dwelling building; it has been built 5 years ago under the thermal regulation RT2012, so the construction is well efficient regarding the heating consumption. The chance is that a small group of stakeholders is really motivated to understand how the systems are running. Even if they are skill in physics, they have no knowledge in building efficiency.

Due to the difference between the design of the energy system and the usage of the building, there are a lot of waste in energy, especially on the hot water production and use. This is typical of this kind of building error design in mountains. The system is schedule for a continuous use and only 20% of stakeholders live in the building 100% of the time.

3 years ago, they add a 45kWp solar power plant under a contract purchase to EDF.

Within Neon project we will optimize the use of energy and introduce 2 new services Energy community and demand responses facilities.

It appears that discussion about sharing energy in communities wakes up energy efficiency issues thanks to the analysis of the usage of energy.

100% Self consumption service (see Table 5) has the goal to maximize the local energy consumption while reducing a large part of energy consumption from the grid. This service need both the right design to synchronize solar power plant and usage needs while the usage level requires to help occupants to decide when the right moment is to consume energy.

This service requires solar powerplant design skill, building energy knowledge and sociological skill to help customers behaviour's change.

Mainly social building owner are interested in this service, but also solar power plant installer could be interested to bring a new service for customers.

Extended community service (see Table 6) came as evidence after we explain the cycle of consumption of different building types. As the participants are aware of energy is was really easy to convince them that extending the community all around in Villard de Lans could be an opportunity to develop an energy mix for optimize the global building efficiency and also to disseminate the self-consumption process.

The question that remains is how efficiency will be improve in an extended community? Again, mathematics will be a suitable way to optimize the community.

The goal of **dynamic audit service** (see Table 7) is to understand the cycles of a complex energy system. While the excel spreadsheet allow to understand in a global point of view on the consumption, the dynamic measurement of energy flows give the dynamic of energy.

To setup this, it is necessary to install sensors on the different energy production and consumption points of measurement and after the data collection process a deep analysis. We can expect than statistical analysis or MCDA will permit to discover new source of optimization.

Table 5 Cross sectoral arrangement for 100% Self consumption service in CEC-02

Energy Service	100% Self consumption services
Stakeholders	Syndic, conseil syndical and residents
Arrangements	Contract with Enedis. A contract has been signed with Enedis to inject power to grid. In regard to energy worldwide context and increase costs of energy, this agreement became less interesting than the self- consumption. So, it is necessary to involve the whole part of residents in a self-consumption schema modifying the actual Enedis contract, but also change priorities between all the usage of energy.
Description of the arrangement	This arrangement involves participants in a PMO (that could be the conseil syndical) in a global contract on sharing energy. Only the PMO as the link with Enedis to setup a new self-consumption contract. 1. need to manage energy sharing between residents 2. need to manage the best us of energy to avoid grid injection 3. Maintain stakeholder attention 4. monthly reporting to Grid manager
User requirements	User acceptance and information
Technical requirements	No specific technical requirement
Law Reference / Legislation	The law applicable is the “code de l’énergie” available on this site: https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr
Main Barriers	Residents' acceptance
Grid relevant aspects	Should be <500KWp

Table 6 Cross sectoral arrangement for Extended Community in CEC-02

Energy Service	Extended community	
Stakeholders	Syndic and conseil syndical	DDLS' neighbours and city of Villard de Lans
Arrangements	Extending the community needs to analyze energy use in DDLS and to understand how to share the rest of energy with participants around DDLS with a distance less than 2 km. The contract is the same that in DDLS community, just with new participants around. These participants could be consumer or producers. The fact is Villard de Lans is a small mountain city and is include in a diameter less than 2km with already existing solar power plant.	
Description of the arrangement	The arrangement is done on the basis of the standard arrangement "PMO" Personne Morale Organisatrice. It is necessary to be compliant with the Law and to be either a social house company, an association, or a syndic	
User requirements	Wish to use local energy	
Technical Requirements	To have a smart meter	
Law Reference / Legislation	The law applicable is the "code de l'énergie" available on this site: https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr But the law about energy communities is under revision	
Main Barriers	Residents' acceptance	
Grid relevant aspects	Participants should not be more than 2 km apart	

Table 7 Cross sectoral arrangement for Dynamic audit service in CEC-02

Energy Service	Dynamic audit services	
Stakeholders	Syndic and conseil syndical and residents	
Arrangements	In order to improve self-consumption, it is important to control the different flows of energy and to analyze how to use more efficiently solar power plant. For this it is necessary to install the right flows measurement sensors. Thanks to the right measurement it will be possible to understand how we can share in the best efficient way energy.	
Description of the arrangement	Energy audit and flow sensors installation	
User Requirements	No specific user requirement	
Technical Requirements	The most difficult requirement is to setup a good image of energy flow with sensors	
Law Reference / Legislation	No specific legislation for this topic	

Main Barriers	Energy skills and data analysis and probably neuronal network usage
Grid Relevant aspects	Not concerned

Thanks to these three topics, CEC-02 will demonstrate that it is possible to link energy communities with energy efficiency. In order to reduce carbon emission these topics are closely linked and of course imply the stakeholder.

The second point is that sharing local energy allows users to be less sensitive to the energy price fluctuation.

5.3 CEC03 – Location: POLÍGONO INDUSTRIAL LAS CABEZAS, Villacañas (Toledo), Spain

The CEC “Poligono industrial Las Cabezas” will be an energy community based mainly on photovoltaic energy.

The energy generated from the photovoltaic installation will be mainly used to supply the following consumption:

- Final consumers, both residential and industrial.
- Batteries, to store the energy in a battery system that provides flexibility to the system.
- Services, for now, to supply energy in periods of lack of power or low irradiance.

Most of the time, the energy will be used to feed different consumptions as well as to be stored, and can be used, according to demand, to feed in a more efficient way the charges made by the electric vehicles that make use of the CEC charger.

The prices faced by different residential consumers will be reflected depending on the time of day, as well as the forecast of the available solar resource. It will also affect the state of charge of the storage system and how it attempts to discharge.

Because depending on the available energy capacity as well as the consumed power, the end consumer will see his energy price reflected.

Something similar will happen to the electric vehicle charger which, depending on the solar resource available as well as the availability of the battery and the time at which charging takes place, will have one price or another for it.

Therefore, the Spanish pilot involves the following main stakeholders (individual and collective ones):

END-USERS: End users may be residential or in some cases recurrent users of the recharge point.

- **End-user (1):** (Residential) Neighbour of the village, with two small children, who is knowledgeable about photovoltaic energy but does not have a roof suitable for an installation. He is looking for an economic saving.
- **End-user (2):** (EV-User) Regular user of the recharging point installed at the CEC, the user is familiar with renewable technologies and understands the proposed operation of the community. He is interested in a constant price for the recharging of his vehicle.
- **End-user (3):** (EV-User) This consumer is a user of the recharging point, which gives high priority to speed, in addition to price, looking for the cheapest possible.
- **End-user (4):** (Residential) this consumer is a resident of the village, who is primarily looking for savings on his electricity bill.
- **End-user (5):** (Residential) this neighbour lives alone during working days in a rented apartment. In addition, his consumption is mostly nocturnal, so he needs to participate in the community and take advantage of the storage system.
- **End-user (6):** (Residential) She is a neighbour who works locally. As her work schedule is usually in the morning, she has the need to consume during the afternoon and evening, so by being part of the community she hopes to be able to save money on her electricity bill.

INDUSTRIAL END-USERS: Industrial users will be those with the highest volume consumption profiles and therefore the most difficult to manage remotely.

- **END-USER: (GFM):** Company in the field of renewable technologies. It will seek to maintain a stable price for its energy consumed and will seek to be able to act on certain consumption at the times it deems appropriate. It can be a good link to introduce new members to the community.
- **EV CHARGING POINT:** It will be a punctual consumer of energy, but of high power and volume, so it is necessary to keep it in mind.

SERVICE PROVIDERS (GFM):

- **EV CHARGING POINT:** Recharging point available in the community, which is intended to be able to provide recharging from renewable energy sources, ensuring the most renewable mobility possible.
- **ENERGY STORAGE:** Energy storage will bring flexibility to the system by helping to make use of surplus energy during periods of zero solar radiation as well as to cover peak demand.
- **ENERGY PV PRODUCTION:** Generation plant which will be the supplier of the renewable energy source. It seeks to be able to provide consumption or at least most of the current members.

Table 8 Cross sectoral arrangement for PV Self consumption service in CEC-03

Energy Service	PV self-consumption system		
Stakeholders	Residential end-users	Industrial end-users (GFM)	Service providers (GFM as PV generator and Battery system provider)
Arrangements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - % Of energy consumed from renewable technologies. - Max. Amount of kWh consumed. - Max Amount of kWh consumed during the day. - Prices of energy depending on the hour when is consumed. - Amount of kWh produced each year (as a compromise of production). 		
Description of the arrangement	<p>% Of energy consumed from renewable technologies: This arrangement could be used as a mechanism of performing how the energy is used. It will also be a way of encouraging the energy consumed by the community to be mostly of renewable origin.</p> <p>Max. Amount of kWh consumed: With this arrangement will guarantee a uniform distribution of the available energy of the community. This measure will also help to determine an average amount of energy consumed per member, thus avoiding energy waste. This measure should not be introduced as a form of rationing.</p> <p>Max. Amount of kWh consumed during the night: This arrangement will be necessary to guaranty the first and second arrangements presented. It will also help determine the power distribution of each member's battery system.</p> <p>Prices of energy depending on the hour when is consumed: The different prices of the consumed energy. A matrix of prices (or a series of multipliers for each member) will be established according to the hours in which energy is consumed.</p> <p>Amount of kWh produced each year: This arrangement is critical to determinate the rest of energy values for the rest of the members. This agreement shall provide for maintenance periods and possible penalties in case of non-compliance with the agreed operating hours.</p>		
User Requirements	<p>Achieve an attractive price for energy.</p> <p>Not to affect your comfort.</p>	<p>Reduce your electricity bill.</p> <p>Not to see your economic activity affected by the changes.</p>	<p>To make a profit that allows the installation to be profitable.</p>

		To be able to promote the installations through the community.	
Technical Requirements	Energy meters and depending on the case, a meter with the possibility of loads management.	Energy meters and depending on the case, a meter with the possibility of loads management.	Integration of the measurements and control of the different equipment in the community's own platform.
Law Reference / Legislation	RD 842/2002-ITC-BT-13-51 RD 15/2018	RD 842/2002-ITC-BT-13-51	RD 842/2002-ITC-BT-13-40-51
Main Barriers	Residential consumers will in general be the most difficult to establish, as their consumption will be the most variable, so in general, it will be more interesting to limit night-time consumption.	The main difficulty in managing these consumers will be instantaneous adjustments, as this will often not be possible given that they are engaged in an economic activity.	
Grid relevant aspects	As there is no need to increase power or modify the installation, there is no relevant aspect. The actions will only be carried out by external control.	This is the same as for residential consumers, no physical actions are required.	Since the pilot already has an infrastructure created and prepared for such use, no changes or extensions will be necessary. Just collect the data.

Table 9 Cross sectoral arrangement for EV recharging station service in CEC-03

Energy Service	EV recharging station		
Stakeholders	External users of the NEON	End-user in NEON	Service providers
Arrangements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Days available (for use most of the year) - Price ranges (Depending on hours of day, renewable power or not) 		

<p>Description of the arrangement</p>	<p>Days available: It is necessary to set the minimum number of days that the charger will be available. This ensures that the amount of revenue is constant throughout the year.</p> <p>Price ranges: It will be necessary to set different amounts depending on when charging takes place, since in the morning it would be charging from renewable sources (cheaper) while at night, charging if it does not come from batteries, would be more expensive. The power will also be a determining factor, as the minimum value to be considered when choosing the load will be the surplus PV power available at that time.</p>		
<p>User Requirements</p>	<p>The main needs of a user of a recharging point can be gathered in:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Competitively priced recharges. - Small recharge time (It is therefore important to incorporate storage to cover these peaks). 		
<p>Technical Requirements</p>	<p>Integration of a price matrix according to the different parameters foreseen. Control of the recharging points according to this matrix.</p>		
<p>Law Reference / Legislation</p>			<p>RD 842/2002-ITC-BT-52</p>
<p>Main Barriers</p>			<p>Communication protocols.</p> <p>As manufacturers work with higher and higher power ratings, this will need to be considered, as available power will be a limiting factor for charging points.</p>
<p>Grid relevant aspects</p>	<p>For external users, needing a good recharging speed requires an appropriate cable section and protections.</p>	<p>For users of the recharge point within the community, a compromise between an affordable price and an acceptable recharge speed is necessary.</p>	<p>The service provider, having the infrastructure already in place, does not really need any requirements other than proper maintenance.</p>

Table 10 Cross sectoral arrangement for Energy storage service in CEC-03

Energy Service	Energy Storage		
Stakeholders	Residential end-users	Industrial end-users	Service providers
Arrangements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Max. kWh storage. - Energy distribution (in percentage) for each stakeholder. 		
Description of the arrangement	<p>Max kWh Storage: A useful capacity of the batteries shall be established, being reserved from the production to guarantee the charging of the batteries on a daily basis.</p> <p>Energy distribution: In order to establish at what times and with what percentage of use, each member can make use of the battery, it will be necessary to carry out a prior study of the consumption, determining the times at which each member can make use of the battery.</p>		
User Requirements	For residential consumers, the main requirement is to be able to take advantage of storage during specific times or when there is low radiation.	For residential consumers, the important thing is to cover peak demand.	For service providers, it is important to have sufficient margin for large consumption moments at the charger.
Technical Requirements	The energy storage system must be scalable, to provide more available power and energy to the system.		
Law Reference / Legislation	RD 842/2002-ITC-BT-13-40-51		
Main Barriers	<p>At times, storage may not be sufficient to serve all members and exclusions may arise.</p> <p>Periodic maintenance of the batteries will be necessary and will affect the daily energy delivery.</p>		
Grid relevant aspects	Lower consumption of the public network.	Consumption €/h much more stable than without being part of the community.	

We can conclude in general that community members, regardless of their role within the community, will require a series of needs to be met in order to be able to participate in the community:

1. Dynamic control of the consumption of residential users.
2. Dynamic control of the consumption of industrial users during or outside working hours.
3. Control of the charging speed of the electric vehicle according to the user's demands and the available generation.
4. It will be necessary to establish hourly prices based on the expected production available as well as for the periods of use of the batteries.
5. Penalties may be established when non-responsible increases in demand affect other users.
6. A loyalty program may be established for community members.

With this set of measures, it will be possible to make the community economically feasible as well as to promote awareness of energy consumption during production periods.

5.4 CEC04 - Location: STAINS City, Stains, France

CEC STAINS CITY is composed of two offices complexes:

- **L'INDUSTREET:** An innovative training campus on the energy professions and trades of tomorrow. Its own PV production 180 kW peak installed on the roof. Regarding production and storage of hydrogen, INDUSTREET is interested in, and they believe it could be developed for mobility and infrastructure.
- **ENGIE CRIGEN building:** ENGIE Corp. Research Centre, working on innovation in the different vectors of energy and develop and own hydrogen technologies.

As defined in D1.2 Service offer co-creation and business planning, and agreed with the CEC stakeholders, STAINS City will be engaged in setting up two main services: (1) collective-self-consumption (see Table 11) and (2) energy compensation by hydrogen production and storage (see Table 12).

STAINS City emerging CEC, is led, being setup-up and coordinated by **ENGIE CRIGEN-Stains**.

The stakeholders involved and participating in CEC STAINS community set-up and on the CEC services implementation and deployment are listed below:

ENGIE-CRIGEN:

- The set-up, the creation and the management of the CEC, STAINS City pilot coordinator.
- Generation, storage H2 and production of electricity via the fuel cells and evaluate how the H2 production could be shared at the community level.

L'INDUSTREET: Provide a renewable and clean energy from the PV installed on the roof of their building, to be used by the CEC according to its needs and manage the agreement with the DSO regarding the power injection.

ENOGRID: Supports ENGIE and INDUSTREET for the technical and administrative set-up of projects and for the collective self-consumption operation and the management of interactions with ENEDIS.

DSO (ENEDIS): Make it power grid available to inject the PV power produced by L'INDUSTREET and responsible of the power balance management.

Table 11 Cross sectoral arrangement for Collective Self consumption service in CEC-04

Energy Service	Collective-self- consumption		
Stakeholders	Engie Lab Crigen / L'Industreet	Enogrid	Enedis (DSO)
Arrangements	Exchange of electricity between the buildings	Collective self-consumption management platform.	Collective self-consumption scheme
Description of the arrangement	Creation of an associative PMO (Personne Morale Organisatrice) between the two for the collective self-consumption operation (mandatory for declaration to the DSO).	Contract between Engie and Enogrid to assist the PMO for the technical and administrative set up of project and for the collective self-consumption operation and the management of interactions with ENEDIS.	Convention of collective self-consumption with the PMO (Engie/Industreet). Manage the community with the DSO: signature of agreement, addition/removal of participants, management of distribution keys, metering.
User requirements	Energy exchange (power) between the two buildings, agreement without remuneration	Provide to the PMO a management platform	
Technical Requirements	Energy meters for injection into the grid.		
Law Reference / Legislation	French regulation for collective self-consumption		
Main Barriers	Geographic perimeter: < 1 km radius between participants Produced power < 3 MWp		
Grid relevant aspects			

Table 12 Cross sectoral arrangement for Hydrogen Power to Power service in CEC-04

Energy Service	Hydrogen Power to Power	
Stakeholders	Engie Lab Crigen	Enedis (DSO)
Arrangements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Production and storage of H2 • Production of electricity thanks to H2 fuel cells 	Injection of electricity into the grid
Description of the arrangement	<p>Maximize the utilisation of PV surplus from L'Industreet by producing H2 thanks to an onsite electrolyser at Engie Crigen.</p> <p>The hydrogen is stored and used to produce heat and electricity thanks to a hydrogen fuel cell.</p>	ENGIE Crigen acts as a producer in the collective self-consumption operation.
User requirements	Produce H2 thanks to PV surplus, and act as electricity producer thanks to fuel cells to exchange energy back with IINDUSTREET..	
Technical Requirements	<p>Electrolyser, H2 storage and fuel cells onsite.</p> <p>Energy management system to optimize the operation of the electrolyser according to the PV surplus.</p> <p>Energy meters for injection of electricity on grid.</p>	
Law Reference / Legislation		
Main Barriers	H2 storage limited to 100 kg to avoid legislation constraints.	
Grid relevant aspects	Works needed to connect to low-voltage grid for power injection.	

This project is an opportunity to demonstrate a simple local energy community exchanging locally produced electricity thanks to PV and H2 production and storage. There is no remuneration defined between the two participants, with arrangements for economic balance thanks to the energy produced on both sides. The aim is to maximise the self-consumption of PV production, and thus the carbon emissions of both buildings.

An energy management system is needed to optimize the operation of the electrolyser according to the PV surplus, and ultimately provide potential flexibility services to the grid (to be evaluated).

6 Conclusion

Under the context of CECs introduced by Directive (EU) 2019/944, the NEON Project aims to coordinate and support activities to enable the technical and business ecosystem for integrated energy services for European Communities to exploit building energy efficiency, renewable energy generation and storage, and demand flexibility to enhance energy savings, reduce CO₂ emissions while improving life quality and the performance of the energy system.

To achieve this goal, it will advance leveraging technologies and develop efficient business model and contracting schemes starting from 4 pilot CECs as early adopters where the following energy services identified in T1.1 will be deployed and evaluated:

- CEC01 – Berchidda: 2 main services (Local Energy Community and Collective PV self-consumption) at Municipality level.
- CEC02 – Domaine de La Source: 3 services (Extend community and Dynamic audit service) at 2 residential buildings level.
- CEC03 – Poligono de Las Cabezas: 3 services (PV Self-consumption, Energy storage and EV recharging stations) at complex of industrial and residential buildings level.
- CEC04 – Stains City: 2 services (Collective self-consumption and Hydrogen Power to Power) at 2 buildings level.

As part of WP1 activities to set the baseline for NEON services concept and development, the objective of this T1.3 was to identify and analyse possible strategies to set multi-actor interactions across sectors for the energy services identified in the CECs in the previous deliverables of this WP1.

The methodology employed in this task and reported in this deliverable to achieve the set goal was to firstly map the different stakeholders and multi-actor in the different sectors of the service energy market (see Section 2), and then the possible cross sectoral arrangements between grid stakeholders/utilities and service providers and between service providers and the community (see Section 3). In Section 4, an overview of social, financial, and technical aspects to be considered for the on-site implementation of the arrangements have been performed and finally in Section 5 possible cross-sectoral arrangements between the specific identified stakeholders for the energy services to be deployed in the CECs were developed and analysed to identify how they will be supported and implemented in practice from a social, technical and financial point of view.

In the overall, the involvement of individual users within CECs, often also as plant owners, together with the fact that such systems can produce economic benefits, will lead reasonably the members of the community to more virtuous behaviours and to a greater knowledge of the basic dynamics that distinguish the production, consumption, and sale of electricity.

In conclusion, this preliminary analysis of the possible cross-sectoral arrangements to implement in practice the identified energy services in each CEC sets the basis for the work that will be carried out in WP2 where more details will be developed in the financial and contractual aspects of the cross-sectoral arrangements and in WP3 in terms of technical implementations to serve in practice these energy services in the CECs.

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